

Local Government and the Changing Urban-Rural Interplay¹.

H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018. Grant Agreement no. 823961

Interview Report

Dear interviewer,

Please use this document to report on the expert interviews. Please do not summarize more than one interview per interview report. Wherever you have added questions, please add them also in this Interview Report. For any questions or concerns, please contact your local coordinator or logov@eurac.edu

Thank you very much!

Informed consent

See *informed consent sheet*

Can identifying information be shared with LoGov researchers?	[yes]
Use of real name for quotes?	[yes]
Archiving of non-anonymized audio-recording	[no]
Archiving of anonymized transcript of recording	[yes]
Archiving of anonymized interview report	[yes]

Basic information

Date of the interview	16/07/2021
Name of the interviewer	ALFONSO EGE A DE HARO
[Name of the expert, check consent above]	TERESA MUELA TUDELA
Affiliation of the expert	ANDALUSIAN FEDERATION OF MUNICIPALITIES AND PROVINCES
Position/Job description	SECRETARY-GENERAL
Gender	FEMALE
Years of experience	MORE THAN 5 YEARS
Area of expertise	MANAGEMENT
Rural and/or urban focus	RURAL AND URBAN

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Part A: Introduction and General Questions

INTERPLAY BETWEEN URBAN AND RURAL MUNICIPAL GOVERNMENTS

1	<p>In your opinion, are there differences between rural and urban local entities in relation to their interests or main concerns? If so, what are the main differences between rural and urban governments?</p>
	<p>There is not a rural cleavage due to certain political initiatives such as the plans for employment guarantee. These plans were implemented in rural areas in order to guarantee employment and a basic rent. These plans serve as settling mechanisms that mitigate the rural-urban divide. In addition, such a plan locates the local governments at the center of the regional government' activity. Independently of the type of municipality (i.e. rural and urban areas), all share a common interest in raising financial resources for the local level via a vis the regional government.</p>
2	<p><i>Do these differences have any consequences on the organization of the association? What mechanisms are in place to ensure equal representation between rural and urban municipalities?</i></p>
	<p>There is no dimension of conflict and 80% are considered rural areas, so that, except for the capital cities of each of the provinces, a certain degree of homogeneity is observed at the local level. The organization seeks balances in the representation of the municipalities based on territorial and ideological criteria, but there is no corresponding impact on the functioning of the organization.</p>
3	<p>Do all the local authorities of the Autonomous Community participate in the association?</p>
	<p>Yes, all municipalities, autonomous local entities are members of the Federation, and consequently of the FEMP.</p>

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OPERATION OF THE ASSOCIATION

4	<p>What is the main source of the association's financial resources? What is the importance of the regional and general levels of government in terms of financing?</p>
	<p>In addition to the contributions of the partners and the fund provided by the Regional Government of Andalusia, the Federation is oriented towards capturing resources through European programs in which it also intends to develop public-private partnerships in which the private actors are not intended to be external consultants but mainly partners in the project. As for the membership, a quota is established on a population basis.</p>
5	<p>Is there a permanent body for the management and representation of local authorities, how are its members elected, are there quotas or guarantees for the representation of less populated local authorities?</p>
	<p>The by-laws establish a system of representation with permanent bodies where decisions are adopted by consensus.</p> <p>The main bodies of permanent representation are the Andalusian Municipalist Council (territorial representation, equivalent to the Territorial Committee of the FEMP) and the Executive Commission.</p>
6	<p>What are the main mechanisms used by the association to identify priority issues?</p>
	<p>The agenda is set by the presidency of the federation and, to a large extent, by the alignment of the European projects where the funding is located. The fact that the Federation is deeply associated with the regional administration and participates, as a basic instrument to defend local autonomy, in surveilling legislative projects does not mean that it is the regional government that determines the agenda. Furthermore, the federation has different mechanisms to influence legislative projects. The federation of municipalities frequently participates, as a regular counterpart, in the working groups and commissions created by the regional government. This "insertion" of the federation in consultative bodies expand its influence over the regional government.</p>

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7	<i>Are working groups created on specific issues -population, aging, social services, digital agenda-?</i>
	Yes, depending on the agenda and projects and where the different municipalities participate on a voluntary basis. In this way, it is possible to overcome the staff limitations of the association.
8	What role does party affiliation play in the decision-making processes within the association?
	Ideological affiliation plays a very important role, but the logic of consensus prevails in the system of adopting agreements in the Federation. The General Secretary's Office focuses on the identification of common problems that arise regardless of the political color of the municipal governments. Once again, participation as an interlocutor of the autonomous institutions and the management of projects (euros) manage to identify municipal interests as opposed to ideological interests. The association tries to achieve consensus in the previous stages (elaboration of the agenda) in order to give priority to municipality interests as opposed to an ideological interest.
9	Which decision rule is most frequently used within the association: majority vote, unanimity, consensus?
	Consensus; when matters come to the assembly they have been previously agreed upon, which shows the importance of the association.
10	Are there mechanisms to ensure compliance with the agreements?
	As a consequence of the importance of consensus, agreements are "self-executing" in nature.

Part B: Questions on Specific Practices

RELATIONS WITH OTHER LEVELS OF GOVERNMENT

11	Which level of government - regional, general government - is the one with which you have the most direct relationship?
	Regional and European levels.
12	What type of relationship is the priority: technical, financial, etc.?

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	<p>The main types of relationship are both financial and technical in scope; in the latter case, the FAMP plays an essential role in the execution of projects or in receiving expressions of interest from private actors, the objective of the FAMP being to create a network of actors ("map of actors") that allows the identification of the most relevant actors according to the project in question.</p>
13	<p>Is there any permanent coordination body with the Autonomous Administration? If so, what is its purpose? analysis of legislative projects? follow-up of program execution?</p>
	<p>The effective participation of Local Governments in regional policy has an important exponent in the intervention during the drafting phase of regional legislation. This participation is very relevant through the reports issued by the Andalusian Council of Local Governments (CAGL), provided for by the Andalusian Council of Local Governments (CAGL), provided for and regulated in article 57 of Law 5/2010, of 11 June, on Local Autonomy in Andalusia, as a purely local body with a purely local composition, and, where appropriate, by the Andalusian Council for Local Agreement (CACL), provided for and regulated in article 57 of Law 5/2010, of 11 June, on Local Autonomy in Andalusia, as a body with a purely local character and, where appropriate, by the Andalusian Council for Local Coordination (CACL), created by Law 20/2007, of 17 December, by virtue of the provisions of Article 95 of the Statute of Autonomy for Andalusia, as a joint body with representation of the Regional Government of Andalusia and the Local Councils of Andalusia, whose functions were the Andalusian Local Councils, whose functions were modified by Law 5/2014, of 30 December.</p> <p>Within the legislative procedure, and in the hearing procedure foreseen in the Regulations of the Andalusian Parliament, the FAMP appears before the corresponding Parliamentary Commissions to express its position regarding the laws of Acts. Furthermore, FAMP intervenes by issuing a mandatory report in the processing of the following specific procedures (i) Files on authorised local prices, (ii) Files on authorised advances, (iii) Reports on municipal ordinances on street trading.</p>
14	<p>What role does the FEMP play in relation to the association? technical assistance? financial? other?</p>
	<p>There is a relationship in terms of sharing experiences, but each federation has its own program. The FAMP does not require the FEMP to have influence at the European level but has its direct contacts with members of the Commission. The FEMP acts more as a counterpart with the central government.</p>

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15	Are there relations with other organizations? Universities? Business associations? Trade unions?
	There are many agreements with other relevant actors and, to a large extent, derived from the management of the projects carried out by the FAMP.
16	How do you guarantee the protection of local autonomy in relation to the acts of other public administrations?
	The protection on local autonomy is achieved through two main mechanisms. First, the promotion of local interests is obtained through the participation in the legislative process (surveillance of regional law). Second, the Federation operates as a communication belt for transferring demands from the local level to the regional level (more than 2,000 programs for the EU next generation compiled).
17	What type of relationship exists with the European and international level in general? Is this relationship coordinated directly or through the FEMP, the State General Administration?
	The relationship is handled in a direct way.

Part C: Additional Country-Specific Questions

CHALLENGES AND FUTURE PROGRAMS

18	What are the main organizational challenges facing the association?
	The main objective is to be useful to the partners, i.e. local governments (not to be perceived as an organization that prevents funds from reaching them directly); to get more funding (to manage a higher percentage of the projects).
19	What are the main public policy challenges - social services, depopulation, etc. - faced by the association?
	The main challenge is to obtain more economic resources to manage. With regard to depopulation, the agenda has not yet been concretely defined, although the model ((i) top-down and (ii) focused on projects rather than regulatory acts) is being followed.
20	What measures are being promoted by the association with a view to achieving a population balance and combating depopulation? Are there differences between local authorities with respect to the measures to be adopted in matters such as depopulation?
	The issue of depopulation (depopulation) is relatively recent on the federation's agenda due to the settlement of the population thanks to the employment guarantee programs. A program with

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	43 measures has recently been presented (Subcommission for the challenge of depopulation). In 2018, the urban exodus to the coast and the depopulation of the interior are already evident in what is a different dynamic to that of other regions.
21	What measures are being taken by the association in order to be eligible for and participate in the European funds for recovery and resilience?
	The measures started to be implemented (without directives but based on the thematic lines / driving projects) in September 2020. The Federation prioritises those initiatives that have a supra-municipal or regional character in order to be more efficient (not all municipalities have to have the same services).

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